

Girdle Paw Pairs	Statistic	Stand (s)	Stand Index	Max Contact At (%)	Max Contact Area (cm ²)	Max Contact Max Intensity
AP1						
RF-LF	Mean	0.24117868	-3.056539	45.1871247	0.35715976	148.168175
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.21750342	-5.8168108	35.2527719	0.2413596	144.269841
AP2						
RF-LF	Mean	0.19121576	-3.8534233	40.3850407	0.4021229	160.882353
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.19824519	-6.7152609	31.2387978	0.32628852	169.454701
AP3						
RF-LF	Mean	0.17120238	-3.4200459	41.7743372	0.3870255	150.44289
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.16501046	-8.5118926	31.9473507	0.36855497	160.297536
AP4						
RF-LF	Mean	0.22911184	-3.2028651	39.8588832	0.44424044	169.969697
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.19822083	-5.9815743	29.739367	0.32785377	155.842735
AP5						
RF-LF	Mean	0.16487625	-5.2512225	37.4885348	0.41875572	151.436364
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.16293857	-8.2466917	30.6678341	0.36799443	163.91342
AP6						
RF-LF	Mean	0.15526597	-3.4750818	38.5120327	0.40764752	154.42735
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.15405361	-8.7836395	24.5774023	0.41352939	167.820971
AP7						
RF-LF	Mean	0.22688825	-2.6215534	50.7099517	0.39551408	152.77895
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.23631606	-6.3110947	35.2989605	0.33294694	166.270022
AP8						
RF-LF	Mean	0.17437484	-3.3057811	38.1482284	0.39116324	148.127273
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.15628916	-6.9576261	24.0221091	0.30363422	155.267677
AP9						
RF-LF	Mean	0.15343217	-4.5522428	46.5032981	0.40015855	160.360606
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.13618685	-8.9610646	33.5138554	0.30051813	159.992308
AP10						

RF-LF	Mean	0.13312861	-7.4300427	41.1172997	0.31212112	137.856838
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.14666811	-13.221686	41.9948023	0.23473663	139.25

Max Contact Mean Intensity	Print Length (cm)	Print Width (cm)	Print Area (cm ²)	Max Intensity At (%)	Max Intensity	Min Intensity
73.9185286	0.88813736	0.80392784	0.45436192	53.2820743	154.084357	36.4662788
73.4052041	0.69902058	0.65269175	0.29828449	48.0171172	153.973138	39.8241758
80.2806234	0.86998147	0.79299187	0.46903516	59.0724615	171.1	36.7980392
78.9956725	0.87416524	0.77612521	0.38615003	42.7897736	175.316239	40.5487179
74.9085583	0.8776801	0.90779645	0.48177765	54.0833546	159.752914	36.2587413
72.4840733	0.94111666	0.90717032	0.4441663	47.4186943	165.048785	37.7788878
84.0150837	0.95222511	0.87405588	0.54035974	52.0008388	178.70303	36.2121212
76.3880509	0.8375177	0.72946409	0.39328915	43.0483803	161.065385	40.9794872
75.409725	0.91648918	0.83830329	0.4905107	54.4392647	159.725758	36.2833333
75.7188305	0.94769594	0.85606297	0.46273369	46.8996532	169.549784	37.5372294
78.1109974	0.94009463	0.86428793	0.50968728	49.2375622	168.185897	36.3760684
78.8959849	0.83662884	0.89164621	0.47147824	38.0105694	172.073489	40.5155678
75.6551105	0.91306612	0.93659555	0.5106435	59.6760004	165.205898	37.0013528
81.0736414	0.86401103	0.78083544	0.41963135	44.8994469	172.53355	40.9756494
75.4430941	0.91701077	0.90479763	0.50065182	53.3101562	158.332867	36.5114219
74.3858911	0.78221982	0.69246071	0.35880509	37.0257935	159.923232	39.1959596
75.6302167	0.91062482	0.87465565	0.48955555	54.5505881	166.578788	36.4969697
76.2965712	0.85969231	0.81706294	0.37651981	45.0803204	165.697436	38.7589744

71.0858534 0.78308913 0.76335331 0.37377635 52.6601429 144.985043 36.982906

69.7544618 0.72571429 0.73121212 0.27851424 47.1590174 144.305556 38.0833333

Mean Intensity	Mean Intensity of the 15 Most Intense Pixels	Swing (s)	Swing Speed (cm/s)	Stride Length (cm)	Step Cycle (s)	Duty Cycle (%)
79.9094443	130.621454	0.15713243	36.7789967	5.62096253	0.39577384	58.5655586
80.0074713	126.216341	0.14698669	33.44601	4.99423175	0.36070582	55.5388845
86.7275706	142.738274	0.12449559	50.952743	6.16502306	0.31982817	58.6664862
84.4834607	143.009345	0.10603942	48.786985	5.24683484	0.30168278	57.6014633
80.2745211	130.9669	0.13516124	50.8938878	6.78908936	0.30794063	55.8783809
77.7252011	131.563464	0.12192246	50.8639427	6.29555834	0.28189756	55.3369782
91.167256	153.435556	0.16067786	47.5826207	7.1506042	0.38846227	57.4848244
83.772643	135.271636	0.13165257	43.3185522	5.97621405	0.33047778	58.7391091
80.6291609	131.410842	0.13134974	57.2500164	7.21847792	0.29138426	54.0056289
80.9402792	139.708687	0.12895768	57.0248643	6.98901075	0.27731181	52.1066394
83.7150988	138.713105	0.13008124	48.5585734	6.10305696	0.28606176	54.206268
86.2646489	145.09794	0.10076453	52.0033305	5.33468458	0.25179614	58.2616604
83.9116515	136.754022	0.17580726	38.155807	6.03365582	0.39981267	56.0721361
86.1556728	146.31721	0.09132719	57.26796	5.00904496	0.3244909	62.4297022
81.6944553	133.528827	0.15300385	46.9879603	7.09728565	0.32602905	52.7872472
80.6390421	130.330685	0.13950693	45.105694	6.23627607	0.28942584	53.3005917
81.6163831	136.681818	0.13118292	58.0524087	7.51177791	0.28250894	53.4041971
81.2329926	136.681258	0.11973681	53.5328842	6.58844657	0.25030226	52.4531033

75.7673596 115.32792 0.14183373 45.4366622 6.23832422 0.27617855 48.1343453

73.639645 113.90054 0.14013036 50.331713 6.39851322 0.28624804 51.2963717

Toe Spread (cm)	Intermediate Toe Spread (cm)	Manual Print Length (cm)	Paw Angle Body Axis (°)	Paw Angle Movement Vector (°)	Single Stance (s)	Initial Dual Stance (s)
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.15713243	0.04163346
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12290601	0.04267289
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12449559	0.0354832
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09910366	0.04862035
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13109902	0.02053713
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.1164531	0.02253728
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.16050141	0.0351867
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.11738772	0.03961095
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12985576	0.01510385
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.128672	0.01605377
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12941627	0.01279857
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09773603	0.02660745
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.17030665	0.02336818
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.08595209	0.07228548
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.14856645	0.01220693
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13333433	0.01604609
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13044437	0.009956
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.11230452	0.01173877

#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12560019	0.004567
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#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.1145435	0.01495387
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Terminal Dual Stance (s)	Body Speed (cm/s)	Body Speed Variation (%)
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0.04197238	13.426503	22.079467
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0.04538917	13.6719401	21.8016637
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0.03514812	19.5611081	23.2914022
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0.05243518	19.4389272	20.9600134
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0.01942985	21.4151016	7.17316189
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0.02307143	21.2708316	8.24312239
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0.03475671	18.4515239	15.2742604
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0.04044886	18.3228776	15.6854762
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0.01212834	23.9636457	18.5364589
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0.02017422	23.6752276	19.1528754
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0.01313034	21.4919274	9.03114714
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0.02692553	21.6588806	10.3651901
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0.02559053	15.6066538	23.4988827
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0.07448939	15.6040053	24.9808926
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0.01405639	20.9275022	11.5491588
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0.01626384	20.8318067	12.0834976
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0.01253825	25.6722491	7.64809339
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0.01345228	25.4763943	9.51059086
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0.00426445 22.4631484 9.41824766

0.01628358 22.4122329 9.47293067

Unit	Step Sequence				
	Patterns	CA	CB	AA	AB
	#	%	%	%	%
AP1	5.33333333	0	25.5555556	31.1111111	32.2222222
AP2	5	20	36.1111111	0	43.8888889
AP3	5	50	8.33333333	0	33.3333333
AP4	3.66666667	8.33333333	36.1111111	8.33333333	47.2222222
AP5	4.33333333	30	16.6666667	0	53.3333333
AP6	5.33333333	48.8888889	12.2222222	33.3333333	5.5555556
AP7	5.33333333	0	52.7777778	25	22.2222222
AP8	5	33.3333333	13.3333333	31.1111111	22.2222222
AP9	4.33333333	6.6666667	31.6666667	0	61.6666667
AP10	5.66666667	26.6666667	22.2222222	51.1111111	0

RA	RB	Regularity Index
%	%	%
11.1111111	0	83.0532213
0	0	83.8095238
8.33333333	0	93.3333333
0	0	79.7368421
0	0	93.3333333
0	0	87.6521739
0	0	75.3812636
0	0	92.4448101
0	0	94.7089947
0	0	100

Girdle Paw Pairs	Statistic	Stand (s)	Stand Index	Max Contact At (%)	Max Contact Area (cm ²)	Max Contact Max Intensity
AV1						
RF-LF	Mean	0.21831272	-2.379326	35.3980093	0.38677439	135.787879
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.19563793	-7.6733412	32.6634692	0.24964047	128.4662
AV2						
RF-LF	Mean	0.14736641	-4.8844965	35.5704389	0.3956343	133.193333
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.12695009	-9.9139332	28.4376802	0.27931488	146.572494
AV4						
RF-LF	Mean	0.19105895	-3.0341982	34.1169615	0.32532653	140.123566
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.2109181	-7.4220522	31.819385	0.29588989	163.428166
AV5						
RF-LF	Mean	0.32216782	-2.1470496	49.4658023	0.411272	161.460317
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.22518026	-6.1018584	28.9445005	0.27373037	152.930556
AV6						
RF-LF	Mean	0.26939815	-2.4718479	35.7868805	0.41654384	149.057239
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.1921571	-6.4131547	33.7000979	0.15395656	109.55817
AV7						
RF-LF	Mean	0.38069422	-2.2578617	48.8053315	0.40172571	136.81039
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.29574958	-5.3340358	31.4944107	0.26369793	133.97037
AV8						
RF-LF	Mean	0.19326637	-3.2727816	40.173037	0.40304384	152.596154
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.19116839	-7.7230309	29.6481641	0.33545496	155.279487
AV9						
RF-LF	Mean	0.56134704	-2.8332709	52.8640907	0.33427343	130.554598
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.78389239	-3.8394359	33.9192442	0.28321015	124.251748
AV10						
RF-LF	Mean	0.22876605	-2.3758936	42.2989425	0.38352508	145.25
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.19693874	-4.9722685	30.3229331	0.28216844	144.785714

Max Contact Mean Intensity	Print Length (cm)	Print Width (cm)	Print Area (cm ²)	Max Intensity At (%)	Max Intensity	Min Intensity
71.8165846	0.86865801	0.87765447	0.46391164	56.1672478	145.121212	36.2424242
67.1218862	0.71063048	0.79599431	0.30582399	43.7055379	133.932401	39.2331002
69.9781221	0.89961693	0.90736277	0.47474874	55.1146638	140.362222	36.2111111
72.6674977	0.73585427	0.78050502	0.32586721	37.4956521	151.365245	40.76338
72.477603	0.77667221	0.77604619	0.39054468	45.4593786	147.931765	37.0204116
79.4040265	0.78815399	0.7923443	0.35359224	43.1725229	168.603693	41.4377029
81.1282548	0.91626228	0.82729334	0.49591399	58.5154154	169.40873	36.2380952
78.6981674	0.73903345	0.7263557	0.32243988	38.3135405	158.52004	43.2069444
75.9643099	0.87863556	0.85649613	0.47218355	58.2429518	158.430976	36.5025253
63.3013483	0.59643389	0.53183888	0.19501398	36.6284196	112.98733	39.8788336
73.769084	0.90975215	0.83307202	0.48494908	66.5285637	147.96176	36.4818182
69.6923861	0.81674855	0.70585226	0.34479971	47.3843012	143.353439	39.2169312
77.519316	0.91011498	0.78900988	0.47414515	59.922643	164.450855	36.775641
75.4494935	0.83891331	0.73823243	0.3815634	41.5975862	159.607692	39.8769231
74.3513123	0.76280436	0.8142484	0.39749367	60.0228162	141.034483	38.3481117
71.9474214	0.80617299	0.60264735	0.34944737	39.9224027	132.632867	42.6608392
75.1127937	0.92730159	0.79443723	0.46315599	57.4560759	157.25	36.7083333
75.0902437	0.80908503	0.66492393	0.33868193	46.413855	153.135714	42.3071429

Mean Intensity	Mean Intensity of the 15 Most Intense Pixels	Swing (s)	Swing Speed (cm/s)	Stride Length (cm)	Step Cycle (s)	Duty Cycle (%)
77.2429563	122.567677	0.16930155	42.6348513	7.00896582	0.38216412	55.3925838
72.8902784	111.766952	0.16020739	36.9513056	6.10873348	0.34480724	51.9437563
74.3658602	118.166815	0.13442601	60.9971288	8.08387954	0.28171805	52.2350471
78.8455125	123.191413	0.12435604	53.4625833	6.91831383	0.2416501	48.3347716
77.5643056	120.835501	0.15211907	40.238107	5.85268017	0.34250103	52.3569912
84.681228	139.394504	0.13950926	40.470072	5.54198135	0.35231446	52.8470896
88.0170108	143.287037	0.20799324	32.0103252	6.04682512	0.5387409	59.1301739
84.2717096	128.702206	0.24737046	29.5288279	4.94028908	0.46348174	53.3332726
82.3467424	132.033838	0.15691841	38.0858688	5.92176249	0.43130304	61.7328583
67.4884682	92.4114467	0.13425539	29.7303953	4.55728133	0.32673646	53.5833756
80.4364123	128.570063	0.17675313	34.6831911	6.00046385	0.57795096	64.5518796
75.5599186	121.338858	0.38220564	30.9114792	6.59674932	0.70334537	51.2968176
84.084713	135.644587	0.14931609	44.4798332	6.15351305	0.34393473	56.2862842
81.7288411	132.450053	0.14225774	42.5542605	5.9284677	0.32781998	54.2347004
81.5314724	121.196976	0.16468929	18.7013284	2.88812938	0.6743187	65.9095675
77.1704578	113.318167	0.18773127	17.5308723	2.67818827	0.88962342	58.9439434
82.572483	132.65	0.18716538	39.1808438	6.67996303	0.41826487	55.2691633
82.5207952	127.402381	0.12890889	36.8322014	5.15584215	0.3246082	55.6489735

Toe Spread (cm)	Intermediate Toe Spread (cm)	Manual Print Length (cm)	Paw Angle Body Axis (°)	Paw Angle Movement Vector (°)	Single Stance (s)	Initial Dual Stance (s)
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.16782157	0.02584725
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.15132603	0.02060503
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.1325036	0.00701957
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.1050455	0.00756408
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.14618668	0.02228648
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12063465	0.04697715
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.20633307	0.05700748
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.15621516	0.02325149
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.15691841	0.05838671
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12279587	0.03491194
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.17675313	0.11227168
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.29095727	0.01682257
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.14871346	0.02220126
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13170723	0.0225234
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.15155581	0.16495634
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13521862	0.27000632
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.17117157	0.03096377
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.14766341	0.0266243

Terminal Dual Stance (s)	Body Speed (cm/s)	Body Speed Variation (%)
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0.02510882	17.8049051	8.05045699
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0.02359406	17.6314824	9.87476072
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0.00627041	27.4196526	9.13211197
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0.00886742	27.1739611	9.80751688
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0.02296664	17.531692	23.2187474
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0.04780912	18.0617651	26.0758843
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0.0605487	11.5778981	40.4494456
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0.03436443	13.4172381	37.8888902
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0.0602461	14.3158202	31.3266119
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0.03626625	13.0138215	33.2915752
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0.11088442	12.7542795	44.4959813
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0.01772836	13.9006082	41.5557357
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0.02183593	18.0200258	13.3615888
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0.02173106	17.883558	15.2850175
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0.21710151	3.97174593	90.04147
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0.33516948	5.48133349	107.05764
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0.03096377	16.3871431	17.60384
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0.02703956	16.7996759	20.4485838
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Unit	Step Sequence				
	Patterns	CA	CB	AA	AB
	#	%	%	%	%
AV1	5	26.6666667	26.6666667	0	46.6666667
AV2	4	35	0	15	40
AV4	5.8	17.33333333	16.6666667	34.6666667	28
AV5	3.66666667	0	19.4444444	19.4444444	52.7777778
AV6	5	13.33333333	13.33333333	13.33333333	53.33333333
AV7	4	42.2222222	0	8.33333333	49.4444444
AV8	4.66666667	22.2222222	0	12.2222222	65.5555556
AV9	5.5	12.5	26.7857143	21.4285714	26.7857143
AV10	3.5	45	0	35	20

RA	RB	Regularity
%	%	Index
		%

0	0	93.9393939
10	0	89.6171802
3.33333333	0	90.088343
8.33333333	0	62.1147741
6.66666667	0	74.9159362
0	0	70.5659075
0	0	83.3714722
0	12.5	38.989899
0	0	66.507177

Girdle Paw Pairs	Statistic	Stand (s)	Stand Index	Max Contact At (%)	Max Contact Area (cm ²)	Max Contact Max Intensity
YA1						
RF-LF	Mean	0.15102402	-6.6296947	49.2299263	0.2664465	113.98254
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.11782686	-12.897699	39.9593772	0.12934897	103.569444
YA2						
RF-LF	Mean	0.12720325	-7.621698	45.5615356	0.31872484	141.142735
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.1264514	-15.930248	34.9667185	0.20943428	159.241667
YA3						
RF-LF	Mean	0.13282306	-8.5539344	42.9656058	0.31138623	134.066667
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.13096954	-15.28809	29.0848443	0.29011505	169.158586
YA4						
RF-LF	Mean	0.13681227	-7.6028212	37.2515278	0.38541421	145.121212
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.13799915	-14.814227	28.7823301	0.33231687	180.588384
YA5						
RF-LF	Mean	0.14505683	-7.8904684	39.3104774	0.40828312	147.090559
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.114985	-13.134626	31.8631194	0.23617086	163.020073
YA6						
RF-LF	Mean	0.17197536	-5.822116	46.6314413	0.34067582	136.905455
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.1221152	-7.8668855	35.7046709	0.13192162	112.184848
YA7						
RF-LF	Mean	0.15121186	-6.7204622	43.1440582	0.31853612	138.618326
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.12149602	-13.183768	32.9913815	0.18412602	132.297369
YA8						
RF-LF	Mean	0.14348766	-7.207739	40.7756699	0.38080539	152.79537
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.12471195	-13.634358	34.9553426	0.23265255	150.347009
YA9						
RF-LF	Mean	0.10879852	-12.046761	43.0297921	0.37681345	146.218485
RF-LF						
RH-LH	Mean	0.08798135	-13.989783	26.1639685	0.25923309	153.818254
YA10						
RF-LF	Mean	0.1614815	-5.6259664	43.4952874	0.28131837	136.520879

RF-LF
RH-LH

Mean	0.17071494	-12.156243	43.4607315	0.19570826	153.147183
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Max Contact Mean Intensity	Print Length (cm)	Print Width (cm)	Print Area (cm ²)	Max Intensity At (%)	Max Intensity	Min Intensity
62.7644006	0.85540212	0.70037188	0.32720634	69.9875456	120.57619	37.8333333
64.5129061	0.63567196	0.46081025	0.16055853	43.3658646	107.169444	40.3847222
69.9639781	0.8422731	0.81091664	0.39269067	45.6881232	144.845299	37.9837607
84.0927592	0.71084722	0.5448355	0.2461576	40.3795753	162.6125	42.2041667
68.2983383	0.89907937	0.81954401	0.3984538	51.5243848	139.755556	37.5222222
83.1034587	0.79449832	0.66633766	0.33064233	37.700746	175.512121	39.8010101
72.5307105	0.91401515	0.84116883	0.46495948	50.5682826	150.343434	36.2525253
84.4396554	0.83643458	0.67073593	0.38718748	36.448673	185.866162	39.2020202
71.6874496	0.93790783	0.8988442	0.47571846	54.6344674	153.024971	36.5695804
86.210974	0.74292785	0.60853487	0.27555167	41.4940251	166.123361	43.7440934
70.6984435	0.90406407	0.85094498	0.41226112	57.7408582	141.661818	36.8472727
69.5846157	0.65605671	0.49952334	0.16759579	53.0998369	119.727273	40.9924242
67.7376289	0.88552967	0.85572659	0.41456714	47.4421314	142.118807	37.0687831
73.7294227	0.69118667	0.6165265	0.22825228	35.1038569	136.516983	40.9305694
71.5673804	0.93862815	0.87522209	0.46128398	47.8996051	156.46229	36.4409091
77.0516165	0.75615914	0.60681604	0.28779882	39.5164376	154.994628	40.4907204
70.4570812	0.90657475	0.89898607	0.4382895	52.8456228	151.245455	37.000101
76.3840474	0.82046032	0.63958153	0.30963196	42.7013794	162.170635	39.4571429
67.7908339	0.81578146	0.76713728	0.35836932	42.987934	140.215834	37.2560363

81.7891694 0.72989277 0.56690502 0.24254883 48.7577381 157.997081 40.5228662

Mean Intensity	Mean Intensity of the 15 Most Intense Pixels	Swing (s)	Swing Speed (cm/s)	Stride Length (cm)	Step Cycle (s)	Duty Cycle (%)
65.2540648	96.8250794	0.11709709	54.069034	6.32771228	0.2676485	56.6686854
67.4465045	87.4737897	0.12418894	42.0047246	5.4637167	0.22680203	46.0025374
72.9916005	116.240342	0.13688429	54.3984774	6.45932193	0.26628508	48.0781195
88.6680542	134.736181	0.11108117	49.5707538	5.80196496	0.239976	45.698074
71.2836939	112.433333	0.10687077	65.5289141	6.79301914	0.22143624	49.9368636
89.5611199	145.060394	0.10670791	62.526642	6.5243961	0.20893547	47.4815791
76.5662488	125.264141	0.1050383	66.4365383	6.7291993	0.2412347	53.6428853
91.186568	154.610774	0.0977301	64.6427137	6.42316198	0.23599868	53.8521124
76.0233392	122.90593	0.10199948	67.0059325	6.25668946	0.25145247	56.0794023
90.4283284	138.756328	0.10699786	49.8509915	5.31409342	0.21943861	46.9022894
74.3857936	119.038182	0.13294984	56.2137288	7.33540708	0.3089478	56.2914619
73.1255453	97.4671269	0.14675511	44.5893922	6.56067715	0.26412626	43.9479307
71.2981843	116.32118	0.12785051	55.6359312	6.84992666	0.28047578	52.9684424
76.2531432	110.847091	0.15277398	43.7081691	6.28081327	0.26902657	44.8760636
75.6947928	126.281094	0.12635129	54.1445401	6.6146866	0.27316192	51.4086706
81.6392163	127.068758	0.10546496	49.2458117	5.46332321	0.2277673	49.9569815
73.7660731	123.276215	0.11826547	77.9819751	7.79130443	0.2300139	47.9105428
82.1000042	130.919008	0.08564768	76.3804035	6.79329554	0.16923167	49.4957706
70.9481642	111.308604	0.13079602	47.3750705	5.52937833	0.2962853	54.4152169

85.4563628 130.507166 0.12912355 42.5640487 5.53809978 0.30588911 49.7272134

Toe Spread (cm)	Intermediate Toe Spread (cm)	Manual Print Length (cm)	Paw Angle Body Axis (°)	Paw Angle Movement Vector (°)	Single Stance (s)	Initial Dual Stance (s)
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.11130525	0.01467555
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09924273	0.00503893
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.10638274	0.01136345
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09000988	0.0226325
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09237909	0.0086958
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09679155	0.00441252
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.10090511	0.01831065
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09419032	0.02750356
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09926829	0.02613199
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.08456876	0.01434959
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.13250548	0.01739401
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12710491	0.00050702
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.12124752	0.01633474
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09852272	0.01301128
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.1194119	0.01313841
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.09356313	0.01685862
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.10752802	0.00136281
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.07566554	0.00628799
#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0.11670392	0.02482135

#DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! 0.09902942 0.03926567

Terminal Dual Stance (s)	Body Speed (cm/s)	Body Speed Variation (%)
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0.01954848	23.1664152	16.23923
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0.01399669	23.6751353	16.1512351
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0.01192215	26.358435	29.3243753
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0.02265065	27.2333915	28.6055246
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0.01994918	30.6664862	17.3878194
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0.01975805	30.6967255	15.8469577
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0.02000802	29.4923829	25.2894861
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0.0279094	29.3186318	25.322584
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0.02360814	26.4377082	32.9963818
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0.01482451	26.062351	32.7184192
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0.01781181	23.5260534	12.1604531
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0.00072838	23.4236334	12.0981196
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0.01485812	24.9214854	13.5252017
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0.01384215	24.7718822	11.7519633
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0.01351243	24.7640632	24.93753
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0.01729592	25.2864196	25.0541628
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0.00136257	38.0230091	26.6630287
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0.00632134	38.6038801	26.4628428
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0.02304104	20.0685744	40.4193856
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0.04214006 20.9929224 37.7317635

Unit	Step Sequence				
	Patterns	CA	CB	AA	AB
	#	%	%	%	%
YA1	5	23.33333333	0	0	64.44444444
YA2	5	35.55555556	5.55555556	21.66666667	20.55555556
YA3	5	16.66666667	26.1904762	33.33333333	23.8095238
YA4	5	33.33333333	6.66666667	13.33333333	46.66666667
YA5	5.2	8	26.33333333	22.33333333	30.33333333
YA6	3.4	5	5	0	66
YA7	4	33.33333333	5.55555556	22.22222222	27.77777778
YA8	5.33333333	9.72222222	19.7619048	59.2063492	6.54761905
YA9	4.4	37	4	45	9
YA10	5.57142857	37.5170068	26.9727891	19.6598639	15.8503401

RA	RB	Regularity Index
%	%	%

6.66666667	5.55555556	86.617184
11.11111111	5.55555556	87.0247229
0	0	98.8505747
0	0	96.8253968
0	13	85.9716376
24	0	78.9803922
0	11.11111111	78.0526316
2.38095238	2.38095238	88.7542088
0	5	90.9979591
0	0	85.8715661